

Guidelines for Seismica copy-editing and layout

For Seismica SCE team

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Steps to copyedit and typeset an article

1. Log in to OJS and navigate to the article page from your dashboard. For now, we will be doing copy-editing and typesetting/layout as a single step, within the OJS “*copyediting*” tab. We won’t use the “*production*” tab at all, unless the Handling Editor sent the manuscript to production. Download the article files from OJS. The files you need are the article text, bib file if it’s already a tex file, and a separate high-resolution file for each figure (png, jpg, or pdf format). [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
 - a. If any of the necessary files are missing, or if the article is not formatted using a seismica template, contact the handling editor (HE) using the OJS “discussion” function, and ask them to request the necessary files from the authors.
2. Check that your conversion scripts and publication template are up to date. Download newest versions from the [github repository](#).
3. If the article text is a docx or odt file, use the seismica-sce toolkit to convert it to a tex file (or ask Hannah to convert it for you). Make any necessary manual corrections (tables, citation errors, figure filenames and widths, etc). The converted tex file will automatically include most (hopefully all) of the necessary metadata macros described in Step 4 [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
4. Create a new overleaf project and upload the article files to it. This includes the article tex file, bib file, and figure files obtained from the author via OJS. **If the author used the Seismica tex template, you will need to switch from the *submission* template to the *publication* template.**

The publication template can be found in the private [github repository for templates, or on the SCE google drive](#). Make sure you have the latest template files downloaded, as we update them periodically.

Copy the (*publication*) files seismica.cls, abbrevnat_seismica.bst (or abbrevnat_seismica_upcasetitle.bst), and the seismica banner image (article or report version) to your working directory. Note that these templates are different from the submission templates! [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
5. Add metadata macros to the article header in the manuscript .tex file (for the doi, volume/issue, editor/copyeditor names, etc). These macros are detailed in the file seismica_template.tex (for the publication template). You will also need to add a “short title” that will be printed as part of the header on each page using the \shorttitle{} command. [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
 - a. The message assigning you to the article should have contained some of the metadata you need: submitted/accepted dates, production editor name, handling editor name, signed reviewer and translator names (if any). Your name also goes in there (as copy/layout editor)
 - b. The DOI will follow this pattern: 10.26443/seismica.vAiB.N, where A and B will be filled in by the volume/issue numbers, and N is the article ID number in OJS (you can find this on your dashboard, listed in the left column of “my queue,”

and it's also part of the article page URL). New issues start every January 1st and July 1st. As of July 2023, we are in v2i2.

- c. If the article is a report, be sure to add the `\reportheader{Report Type}` command with the proper "report type" (e.g. Fast Report, Field Deployment Report, etc), and use the `[report]` option. [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
6. Check that the space between author given names and surnames **for all but the first author** (or the ones at the end of a line) has been replaced with a ~ (tilde, LaTeX for a non-breaking space) so that names will not break across a line.
7. Compile the article using `lualatex` with the `[proof]` option. Fix any LaTeX problems that break compilation (and ask for help if you need it).
8. Adjust layout as needed, making sure figures are correctly set for 1 or 2 column widths, tables are formatted and filled accurately, and equations are properly formatted. [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
9. Make a copy of the article tex file, and proofread/copy-edit the text. Compile a pdf showing your corrections using `latexdiff`. You can also mark up the pdf proof using a pdf annotation tool of your choice. *Don't forget the proof watermark!* [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
10. Start a discussion thread in OJS with the corresponding author and HE in the ***Copyediting tab***. Do not start the discussion in the *Production tab*, the authors won't be able to read it. Send the author the copy-edited proof (using our [\[OJS discussion templates\]](#)) and ask them to approve of the copy-edits and the general layout. Note that if you want to offer style edits, you should ask the authors in advance. [\[detailed steps for discussion in OJS\]](#) and [\[OJS discussion templates\]](#)
11. Iterate on the proofs as necessary until the authors approve them. If there are any issues and the HE doesn't notice or step in, notify the HE separately to ask for help.
 - a. When should you refuse to make some changes? If unsure, you can ask the SCE chairs or the HE. You can refuse changes when the authors ask for something unreasonable, like:
 - i. figure sizes that are not possible within the Seismica template
 - ii. changes to the text that would alter the meaning of the accepted article
 - iii. changes to the formatting that differ from the Seismica look
 - iv. having figures appear at very precise spots in the final pdf (since tex will shift figures to optimize page filling, there's a limit to how precisely we can set things)
 - b. When should you call in the HE for help? If the authors are not responding to messages in a reasonable amount of time (~1 week is reasonable to check proofs, unless more time is requested), or if the authors don't accept your refusal for specific changes. Most of the time we shouldn't need to call in the

HE, as authors tend to be excited to finish up their article and have it published quickly.

12. When the proofs have been approved, notify the HE and work on finalizing the metadata.
 - a. What you will need from the HE: issue/volume numbers (these do not change frequently, double check to make sure you have the right ones) and the publication date (the HE will determine this - should be 7 working days after proofs validation for regular articles, 3 working days after for fast reports, though this can be flexible if needed).
 - b. The DOI will follow this pattern: 10.26443/seismica.vAiB.N, where A and B will be filled in by the volume/issue numbers, and N is the article ID number in OJS (you can find this on your dashboard, listed in the left column of “my queue,” and it’s also part of the article page URL). New issues start every January 1st and July 1st. As of July 2023, we are v2i2.
 - c. Fill in any missing metadata using the metadata macros from Step 4.
 - d. Produce the final PDF galley (without the “Proof” watermark)
13. Convert the .tex version of the galley (=accepted proof) to an xml galley using the tex2jats scripts. [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
14. Use an online bibtex converter (for instance [bibtex.online](#) or <https://asouqi.github.io/bibtex-converter/>) to get the reference list in plain text (one reference per line), and copy it into the text box under “References” in the publication tab. If you think there are references in the bibfile that were not cited in the paper, you can use the [clean_bibfile.py](#) script (included with the docx/odt conversion tools) to create a clean bibfile first.
15. Upload the galley files (PDF, XML) under “Galleys” in the publication tab (along with any supplementary material files the authors provided), and notify the HE that you are done. For the PDF and XML galleys, the galley type is “Manuscript pdf file” (review reports, if you upload them for the HE, are “Other”; supplementary materials are also “Other”). Do not use “manuscript source file” for either the PDF or the XML galley. For the XML galley, use the file with the suffix “_galley.xml” generated using tex2jats. For the PDF galley, OJS will ask you to provide a filename which will be what people get when they download the file. It will auto-populate with whatever the file you are uploading is named; if your filename is something generic like “main.pdf” be sure to edit that display name to match our naming convention: FirstAuthor_year.pdf [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
 - a. For the XML galley, you will also need to re-upload all of the individual figures as dependent files. You do not need to upload separate files for xml tables, they are already in the suffix_galley.xml file.
 - b. Use “PDF” and “Full text” as labels for PDF and XML galleys.
 - c. To preview the article before it is published, click the “preview” button on the upper right of the “publication” tab. This will show you the article page, and

you can also click on the links to view the PDF and XML galleys as they will appear to readers. We highly recommend checking the XML galley to make sure that the figures are linking properly and that the text is rendering as you expect it to.

16. **Archive the source files for compiling the pdf by uploading copies of the final .tex and .bib files to OJS.** You can attach these to a discussion thread addressed to one of the SCE team leads [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
17. That's it! Note that we will not proofread, copy-edit, or typeset supplementary information or materials, and reviewer reports will be compiled by the editors, not us.

Seismica's copy-editing philosophy

Proofreading for clarity: The primary goal of copy-editing is to ensure that papers published in Seismica are clearly presenting authors' work. On the most basic level, this means finding and correcting typos and grammatical errors that were not caught during review.

Reading and editing for style: Copyeditors may also wish to make suggestions for style-related edits to improve the clarity of a manuscript. Proofreaders are not required to offer style edits, but if they want to, they may ask if the corresponding author is interested in receiving some style suggestions, and provide suggestions if the author answers affirmatively. Some authors may prefer that proofreaders only correct typographical errors, so we do need to check before offering style edits. Note that the Guidelines for Editors state that Seismica does not impose any "unnecessary language-based gatekeeping." Poor scientific English which obstructs the understanding of an article is grounds for rejection without review, so anything that makes it all the way to copy-editing should not need extensive editing.

If you need help: Each article will be assigned to one SCE team member for both copy-editing and typesetting, but that doesn't mean you need to do everything on your own – if you have questions about any part of the process, from grammatical edits to LaTeX, please reach out! You can always email the co-chairs (Théa and Hannah), or send a message to the team slack channel. Collectively, we have broad expertise in all aspects of copy-editing and typesetting, so if you're unsure about or stuck on anything, someone else on the team can probably help out.

If you're going out of town: We don't need to know where you're going or why, but if you will be unavailable for an extended period of time, please post that information on the [Seismica board google calendar](#) so that we won't assign you any articles while you're away. All members will be given edit access to the calendar, so be careful and don't delete what other people add.

Sharing proofs: During the typesetting process, we will exchange one or more article proofs with the authors. Proofs using the Seismica publication template should always be generated with a "proof" watermark. The final non-proof pdfs will be made available when they are uploaded to the website for publication in an issue, but we need to make sure that we don't have un-watermarked versions floating around that may differ in any small way from the final version.

Sharing the workload: Part of our model for the proofreading and typesetting process comes from Volcanica - they take justifiable pride in offering detailed spelling, grammar, and style recommendations to authors during this process, and in encouraging more interaction with authors than most journals throughout the production process so that everyone can be proud of and happy with the final product. We would like to offer this to our authors as well, but are mindful of the time burden it can impose on us, the standards and copy-editing team. We'll have to figure out how to balance this as we go along, but the bottom line is, if you feel as though too much is being asked of you or you are getting bogged down on an article, talk to the co-chairs (Théa and Hannah) so we can find a way to help and adjust our guidelines and

processes for the future. To start with, we will aim to assign roughly equal workloads to all team members, looking at both the number of articles each person handles per unit time and the complexity of those articles (in terms of length, number of equations/figures/tables to check, etc). Since we don't yet know what the volume of submissions/accepted articles will look like, we will update our strategy over time to ensure work is evenly distributed. If the volume of submissions turns out to be too high, we will recruit additional team members as needed.

How to...

Find an article I've been assigned to work on

Log in to OJS, or if you're already logged in, use the menu in the upper right corner to go to your dashboard. Article(s) you are assigned to work on will appear in "My Queue."

Image: OJS dashboard for a copyeditor, with an article that is in the "production" stage in their queue. Note that the article ID is to the left of the author name (here the ID is 192).

Convert docx/odt to tex

Scripts for converting files in the Seismica docx/odt template to LaTeX are on github in the [seismica-sce repository](#). To use them, clone or download the repository, install all the dependencies, and follow the steps outlined in the README file. Note that if authors do not use the docx/odt templates properly the scripts may not work, so checking the article file before converting is highly recommended. Also, the scripts try to highlight any spots where the conversion process may not have worked so that you will see/notice them in the compiled pdf, but it's not a perfect process, so you will need to proofread carefully. As of July 2023, branch `crossref` in the github repository has a beta version of the `fix_bibtex.py` script which queries crossref for missing DOIs. Use at your own risk (and let us know how it goes!)

Contributions/improvements to these scripts are very welcome! If you have any ideas (or find any bugs/persistent problems), feel free to raise a github issue, and if you want to change or fix anything yourself, start a new branch and make a pull request.

Note that as of early 2023, tables are parsed semi-automatically!

Set up an overleaf project for a seismica article

Log in to Overleaf, and create a new blank project.

Image: Overleaf user homepage, with “new project” selected at right.

Overleaf will add a `main.tex` file to your project by default. You can delete it by clicking on the three dots to the right of the filename and choosing “delete”. It’s also fine to leave it, but you may need to go to the project menu (upper left corner) and specify that the “main document” is the tex file you uploaded rather than `main.tex`

Upload the publication template style files: `seismica.cls` file, `abbrvnat_seismica_upcasetitle.bst`, and the banner png file for this article (there are banners for regular articles and for reports).

Upload the article content to your project: the `.tex` file, the `.bib` file, and each of the figures.

The screenshot displays the Overleaf web interface for a LaTeX project named 'seismica'. The left sidebar shows the file explorer with the following files: 'abbrvnat_seismica.bst', 'banner.png', 'biblio.bib', 'empty.png', 'seismica_templa...', and 'seismica.cls'. The main editor shows the LaTeX source code for 'seismica.cls', which includes metadata, class options, and document structure. The right pane shows the compiled PDF output, which is a template for the 'seismica' journal. The PDF includes a title page with author information, abstract, introduction, a table, a figure placeholder, and a mathematical equation.

Image: overleaf project with all the files for the publication template, plus an “article file” (here, the publication template with minimal content) and a “figure file” (empty.png). Note the green “Recompile” button above the pdf viewer panel on the right.

Click on “Menu” in the upper left hand corner, and set the compiler to LuaLaTeX. You do not need to set the TeX Live version (v2022 is OK).

Image: Overleaf project with “Menu” open from the upper left corner. The compiler for the project is currently set to pdfLaTeX, and needs to be changed to LuaLaTeX.

(Re)compile the article pdf by clicking the green “Recompile” button.

Add tex commands for metadata to the latex file

To use a file formatted using the LaTeX submission template with the publication template, you will need to add the following commands to the article header (before `\begin{document}`):

```

\reportheader{Fast Report} % use for any kind of report, but not for articles
\receiveddate{1 January 1900}
\accepteddate{29 February 1900}
\publisheddate{4 April 1900}
\prodedname{Production Editorname}
\handedname{Handling Editorname}
\copyedname{Your Name}
%\translatorname{translator, if there is one}
%\reviewername{signed reviewers, if any} \ double slash for newline between names}
\dois{10.100}
\thevolume{0}
\thenumber{0}

```

```
\theyear{2022}
```

And, under the `\title{The full, long, and detailed title of the article}` line, add:

```
\shorttitle{A shortened article title}
```

The commands above have placeholder values, which you'll replace in the final galleys.

The production editor will usually be Gareth Funning; if it's not Gareth, it will either be another Executive Editor (Carmine, Kate, Christie, Sam), a guest editor for a special issue, or the fast reports editor (Kiran Kumar Thingbaijam). The HE should let us know who the production editor is for each article.

Turn on/off the proof, report, and/or breakmath options

The different options for compiling articles are set at the beginning of your tex file, as part of the documentclass declaration. For example:

```
\documentclass[proof,report]{seismica}
```

The “**proof**” option adds a PROOF watermark to the pdf.

The “**breakmath**” option will break up equations that are too long to fit well in a column. If breakmath has issues, you can use the “**onecolumn**” option in a pinch.

The “**report**” option will insert a different banner image and will add the report type (e.g. Fast Report, Software Report, pulled from a subsequent metadata macro) to the article pdf, from the metadata you provide in the `\reporthead` command [\[details here\]](#).

There is an “**invited**” option for invited articles.

There is an “**opinion**” option for editorials/opinion pieces.

To compile a standard article without any of these options, you can just leave out that bracket:

```
\documentclass{seismica}
```

Produce the PDF proof

Note: you will need to compile several times for all of the elements to be taken into account. Overleaf often does this automatically, but if you are compiling on your local machine, you will need to run `lualatex`, then `bibtex`, and then `lualatex` 2+ times to make sure all the citations and internal links are properly linked.

The following are specific things to check to ensure the PDF proof is correct.

Verify metadata, authors info and url links:

- **The proof option is ON (produces a watermark)**
- Url links appear and are clickable in the PDF
- Authors ORCID are correct
- Corresponding author information is printed in the PDF
- Authors contributions (credit) are printed

Verify and modify figures and tables location and size:

- Check [Layout for tables and equations](#)
- Reformat tables if necessary
- Figures: displaying properly with the correct resolution. If the resolution is not high enough, you can ask authors to provide other figure files.
- Figures: adapt their size if necessary (see [modify figure and table size](#))
- Figures and tables: check that captions are present, and that in-text references are linked properly.

Verify bibliographical references:

- No missing reference in the main text (appears with a ?) - reminder: you might have to compile with LuaTeX several times in a row.
- No missing reference in the references list
- Check if DOI is provided and printed for every article/ book. If not, you might have to edit the bib file. If too many references are provided without DOI, you can ask the author to upload another list. You can also use the updated version of [fix bibtex.py in the docx/odt conversion toolkit](#) to automatically query crossref for missing DOIs.
- Check if URLs are provided for references without a DOI.

Layout for tables and equations

- You can use the latex code provided by the authors, provided they use the tabular environment. If they don't use the tabular environment, **make sure to define a style consistent with the Seismica table style** (defined in the cls file) by using these commands within the table environment:

```
\centering
\sflight\small
\arrayrulecolor{gray}
```

- In tables, you can use `\hline` or `\thickhline` for horizontal rules. Also, you can add a `\rule{0pt}{2ex}` after horizontal lines to add an extra vertical space.
- If tables are too complex and have not been provided as in LaTeX format, you can ask the authors to provide a corresponding figure
- If table cells contain long strings of text, one good way to wrap the text is to put a tabular environment inside your table, e.g. after `\begin{table}[ht!]` and `\centering`:

```
\begin{tabular}{m{2.7in} m{1.1in}}
```

where 2.7in and 1.1in are, in this case, the widths of the two table columns. A corresponding `\end{tabular}` should go before your `\caption{}` and `\label{}`. Tex will automatically wrap the text within each cell, but if you don't like its choice of line breaks you can also insert your own in the cell text using `\newline`

- If any equations are too long for the standard two-column format, consider using the `[breakmath]` setting. If figures are being inserted into the reference section, move them up in the text

Modify figure and table size

To include a figure that spans two columns (full page width in the publication template), use:

```
\begin{figure*}[ht!]  
\centering  
\includegraphics[width=\textwidth]{figure_filename}  
\caption{}  
\label{}  
\end{figure*}
```

For a figure that spans only one column in the publication template, use (without *):

```
\begin{figure}[ht!]  
\centering  
\includegraphics[width=\columnwidth]{figure_filename}  
\caption{}  
\label{}  
\end{figure}
```

Similarly, for tables, you can use *table** and *\textwidth*, or *table* and *\columnwidth*.

Convert figures from pdf to png format

Authors may submit figures as pdf files, and that's fine for pdf galley but pdf figures are not compatible with the xml viewer in OJS. So, if you have pdf figure files to work with, you can convert them to the friendlier png format. There are plenty of ways to do this, including free online converter tools (google and pick your favorite) or, if you have imagemagick and like command line tools, a line of code similar to this one:

```
mogrify -verbose -quality 00 -density 250 -format png fig*.pdf
```

replacing the "fig*" with whatever naming convention makes sense for the files you are working with. These instructions can also be found in the tex2jats repository readme file.

Fix text that is spilling out of columns

LaTeX will try to fill text columns using justification and its internal hyphenation rules, but occasionally it will not know how to hyphenate scientific vocabulary and will leave words hanging out of column edges. This can often be fixed with a custom hyphenation rule added to the article preamble (before `\begin{document}`). Some examples are:

```
\hyphenation{ani-so-tropy}  
\hyphenation{sub-duc-tion}
```

Use latexdiff in overleaf

To use latexdiff within overleaf, create a new file named `latexmkrc` with the following text (when you copy-paste this command, you may need to delete and replace the quotation marks manually) :

```
$lualatex = "latexdiff main.tex main_sce.tex > main_diff.tex;  
lualatex %O main_diff"
```

replacing “file_original.tex” and “file_edited.tex” with the name of your initial and copy-edited article tex files. When you compile the article in overleaf, it should produce a pdf with the differences marked.

Use discussion threads in OJS

Navigate to the dashboard page for the article you are working on - it should be in the “Copyediting” stage of the workflow. Scroll down to “Copyediting Discussions” and click on “Add Discussion,” then follow the prompts. You can add participants (copy the HE on all correspondence with the author), set the subject line and text, and attach files (like proofs).

[Templates for OJS discussions are here.](#)

All the discussion participants should receive an email to notify them that they have been added to a discussion (and, when there are replies to a thread, that there are new messages for them), but the text of the messages will not be included in the email - they, and you, will have to log in to OJS and navigate to the discussion thread to see the messages.

Convert TeX to JATS XML

The toolkit for converting publication-ready tex files to jats xml is on github in [the tex2jats repository](#). To use it, clone or download the repo and follow the instructions in the README file. Note that you will have to manually re-add the header of any tables, and possibly have to reformat tables if they are too complex (there are instructions for this in the github page).

0) Before running tex2xml.sh:

- Convert any figure to PNG [\[detailed steps here\]](#)
- Remove any text effect from the title (`\emph`, `\bold`, ...) in the tex file
- Check that you did not use the obsolete command ``seistable`` in the tex file
- ORCID macro should be provided for *all* authors, otherwise ids won't be printed in the JATS galley, and you will need to fill it out manually.
- *[shouldn't be necessary anymore but check author names after conversion] Remove tilde (~) from authors name in the tex file*

1) Run tex2xml.sh:

- If any issue appears, try to fix it. Usually it comes from errors in the template formatting or missing information. If you need help, contact Théa via slack.
- [known issues](#)
- Your first xxx_galley.xml file has been produced without errors.

2) Initial checks: (with a text editor)

- Open it with a web browser, it shouldn't show any error.
- Authors' names and affiliations, editors, reviewers' names are printed properly
- DOI, title, and other metadata are printed properly

- Abstracts look OK
- Cross references for figures (xref) look OK. They should be printed with a format similar to:

```
<xref ref-type="fig" alt="1" rid="fig1">1</xref>
```
- Acknowledgements, list of references looks good
- If Tables, see point (3)

3) If there are TABLES in your TeX galley, `tex2xml.sh` will export two files for each table: `tabxx.tex` and `tabxx.xml`, `xx` ranging from 1 to the total number of arrays present in the article.

-> *If the table is simple and has been converted properly by `pandoc + cleanjats.py`:*

- Check and correct the caption of the table in the xml file for references or formula that have not been converted.

-> *If the table is too complex and has not been properly converted:*

- Correct any unwanted symbol in ``tabxx.tex``
- Translate the ``tabxx.tex`` to HTML with <https://tableconvert.com/latex-to-html>
- Copy the HTML code to the XML table file ``tabxx.xml``, where indicated
- Replace the wrong table code in the XML galley ``proof_galley.xml`` with the updated ``tabxx.xml``. In the XML galley, tables are under a ``table-wrap`` environment.
- Check and correct the caption of the table in the xml file for references or formula that have not been converted.

Once these preliminary checks are done, you can use the preview tool in OJS [see [Steps to copyedit and typeset an article](#)].

3) Final checks: (with the OJS preview tool)

- Title, authors, names of editors, reviewers, and other metadata are printed correctly (in the main text page but also the *info* tab)
- Cross references to figures and tables and references are OK
- Tables are printed correctly
- Acknowledgements are printed correctly
- References (in the *References* tab) are printed correctly.
- [known issues](#)

Contributions/improvements to these scripts are very welcome!

If you have any question, ideas, or find any bugs or persistent problems, feel free to contact Théa directly, or raise a github issue. If you want to change or fix anything yourself, start a new branch and make a pull request.

XML conversion: known issues

- Images won't display if there are "weird" characters in figures' names (eg, "fig+3+rev2.png" or "fig_a&b.png")
- References and maths formula in table captions are often not converted properly
- Often in metadata, credits or acknowledgements: symbols are not properly converted, or are still escaped when they shouldn't: look for `\&`, `\%`, multiple occurrences of dots and/or comma (``..``, ``.`,``).
- In equations, `\mathbf` or `\mathrm` are not parsed correctly. You can remove them from the TeX file and rerun `tex2xml` from scratch, it should work fine.

Notify the HE in OJS when an article is complete

Navigate to the dashboard page for the article you are working on - it should be in the "Copyediting" stage of the workflow. In the "Participants" list on the right side, click on the small blue arrow next to the HE's name. Then, click on "notify" and follow the prompts. This will basically start a new discussion, but will specifically give you access to some OJS email templates for notifying the editor when galleys are complete.

Upload galleys to OJS

Galleys are uploaded in the "Publication" tab in OJS.

Image: add the final article files (pdf, xml, and any supplemental information) with all metadata including DOI etc. in the “Galleys” tab. Each file is an individual galley to be added.

The galley types we will use are “Manuscript pdf file” (for both PDF and XML galleys), “Supplementary Materials” and “Review reports” for those two things, and “Data set” for any data-like supplementary materials. When adding a galley, the 'Galley Label' will show up on the website. We will use 'PDF' and 'Full text' as labels for the article text (capitalized PDF, pdf and xml galleys). For Supplementary Materials, use 'Supplementary Material' as the label. For review reports, use 'Review Reports'. Galleys should appear in the following order (you can modify the order after uploading):

- 1) PDF
- 2) Full text (*not "XML" anymore!*)
- 3) Supplementary Material
- 4-...) Any supplemental data, object, in no specific order
- last) Review Reports

Note that OJS will also ask you to provide a name for the file when you upload the pdf galley. This field will be automatically populated with whatever you named the file, and when people download the file this is the filename they will get. We will use this convention for the public-facing filename: FirstAuthorSurname_year.pdf. For example, for the first paper

Seismica published, this would be: Cottaar_2022.pdf

For the XML galley, note that you can do a batch upload of the figures (dependent files) simply by dropping all files in the upload field (does not work for every browser).

Image: creating a new galley starts with specifying the galley label, which should be “PDF” or “XML” or “Supplementary Material.”

Image: modify the order of galleys with the 'Order' button

Use [an online bibtex converter](#) (with or without using clean_bibfile.py script first) to get the reference list in plain text (one reference per line), and copy it into the text box under "References" in the publication tab. Make sure to press 'save' after you paste the text.

Image: under “References,” copy-paste the bibliography from the article with one reference per line. This is so the references can be indexed by crossref.

Archive the source files

To archive the tex and bib files used to produce the final galleys for each paper, make a discussion thread with either Hannah or Théa (whoever assigned you to the article) once the galleys are complete and attach a zip archive of the tex and bib file you used to compile the pdf (or the two files unzipped, either way is fine).

OJS discussion/email template text for corresponding with HEs and authors

In any of the templates below, feel free to modify the author name and the signature by using your name instead of 'The Seismica copy-editing team'.

Don't forget to attach the proof or any needed file!

First contact with authors for proofs validation

Style edits are optional, so you may leave out the highlighted sentence if you want.

Subject - [Action Needed] Article proof ready for review

Dear Author,

The proof of your article accepted for publication in Seismica is attached for your review. Modifications to your original text have been highlighted. **If you are interested, our Copyediting team would be happy to provide further guidance on style or grammar.**

Please let me know if there are any issues with this proof, or if you would like to make any additional changes. Your article is near completion so no significant changes should be made, but any changes related to copyediting that do not affect the scientific content of the manuscript are fine. This could include:

- moving figures/tables
- adjusting figure size or resolution (figure width can be either 1 or 2 columns)
- correcting spelling errors

Article metadata (doi, dates) will be updated before publication.

Take any time you need to review this proof and reply with your approval or comments. If you plan on taking more than 1 week, please notify us in advance. Feel free to contact us with any questions.

All the best,

The Seismica Copyediting team

First contact with authors **BEFORE** proofs validation

In some cases, you might need to contact authors before proofs validation, if some information is incorrect and you cannot finalize the proofs.

In the template below, modify the text in [] or where needed

Subject - [Action Needed] Article files needed for production

Dear Author,

Your article submitted to Seismica is being copyedited and formatted for publication. Unfortunately, we are currently unable to finalize the proof because of the following issue(s).

[describe the issue(s)]

Please [(upload the updated files to OJS) OR (provide responses to these queries)] when you are ready.

Take any time you need to respond. If you plan on taking more than 1 week to submit your updates, please notify us in advance. Feel free to contact us with any questions.

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The Seismica Copyediting team

Refuse change asked by the authors

Be sure that the HE is copied on this message/discussion

Dear [Author],

Thank you for reviewing your article proofs. Unfortunately, we are unable to make all of the changes you requested because they do not fully comply with our policies. Specifically, we cannot do the following:

[list things that can't be changed and, briefly, why]

We will make the other corrections that you have requested to the proof, and proceed from there. If you have any questions, feel free to respond to me and to the handling editor.

All the best,

[your name]

Request metadata from HE

Dear [Editor],

The authors have validated proofs for this article, so we can move to the last pre-publication tasks. To fill in the remaining article metadata, I will need you to send me the projected publication date (see the Seismica [Editor Guidelines](#)/HE checklist for more info) and confirm the volume and issue number for this article.

Once I have this information, I can make the final PDF and XML galleys for upload. You will also need to compile the reviewer reports into a PDF and either upload it as a galley or send

it to me for upload, and will need to notify the media & branding team that the article is in production if you have not already done so. There is more information about all of these steps in the [Editor Guidelines](#), in the “Production Workflow” steps, and in the Handling Editor guidelines.

All the best,

[your name]

Notify the HE when galleys are ready

You can use the OJS template for this by clicking on “notify editor” in the participants list for the article, or start a discussion thread separately.

Dear [Editor],

The final PDF and XML galleys for this article are complete, including the target publication date provided by you, and I have uploaded them to OJS. I have also filled in the plain-text reference list for the article metadata in OJS, so at this point my tasks are complete. Please let me know if you find any issues with the galleys that need to be corrected before publication.

All the best,

[your name]

Resources and links

- [Toolkit for converting docx/odt to tex](#)
- Seismica LaTeX publication template - please do not share these files outside of SCE
 - [github - ask for access](#)
 - [google drive](#)
- [Seismica style guide](#)
- [Overleaf](#) (and [Overleaf documentation](#))
- [Tool for getting plain text references out of a bib file](#) [and [clean_bibfile.py](#) to generate a clean bib file without any unused references]
- [Toolkit for converting tex to jats xml](#)
- [OJS documentation](#)
- [Seismica board google calendar](#)
- Some LaTeX resources:
 - a list of resources: <https://shantoroy.com/latex/latex-resources-in-a-nutshell/>
 - LaTeX quick start guide: <https://latex-tutorial.com/quick-start/>
 - a "learn LaTeX in 30 min" tutorial: https://www.resurchify.com/latex_tutorial/latex_quick_guide.php
 - another "learn LaTeX in 30 min" https://fr.overleaf.com/learn/latex/Learn_LaTeX_in_30_minutes
 - LaTeX cheat sheet <http://wch.github.io/latexsheet/>
- Some other convenient tools:
 - Downthemall, allows batch download (download all source files in OJS in one step!): <https://www.downthemall.net/>
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